

Origin, evolution, and maintenance of gene-strand bias in bacteria

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DESCRIPTION OF CODE USED IN THE INVERSION WORKFLOW

1. Inversion Detection Pipeline

- Rename files to remove the suffix (run for whole genome fasta, gene-wise fasta, .faa, and .gff files):

Script: [rename_files.py](#)

- Remove plasmid sequences:

Script: [excludeplasmid.py](#)

- GC-skew based ori-ter prediction (requires executable C program file [findori_windowcontrol.out](#) for linux based OS):

Script: [findori_pipe_windowcontrol.py](#)
Output: [/originresults/resultsummary.txt](#)

- Find Dif and DnaA boxes using blast and string matching:

Script: [blast4dif_and_dnaa.py](#)
Output: [/ori_dif_info/oriter_vs_dnaadif_predictions.txt](#)

- Edit .gff files to tabulate and determine gene orientations:

Script: [createnebdb.py](#)
Output: [/edited_gff3s/*_edited.gff](#)
[/gff_edit_for_genes/*_edited.gff](#)
[/gff_edit_for_genes/genomesummary.csv](#)

- All-vs-all blast for finding core genes (ensure outgroup.faa file is **not** in the same directory):

Script: [blast4ortho.py](#)
Output: [codes/blastresults/*](#)

- Create core genome from blast files:

Script: [generate_coregenome.py](#)
Output: [final_blastresult.csv](#)

- Add gene coordinates and directionality info to the core genomes:

Script: [append_direction_tags.py](#)
Output: [direction_coregenome.csv](#)

- Get bidirectional blast hits between reference and outgroup (in outgroup folder):

Script: [blast4ortho.py](#)

- Create core genome with the outgroup:

Script: [gen_out_core.py](#)
Output: [outgroup_coregenome.csv](#)

- Determine inversions based on GC-skew and directionality disparity, compare and retain the common:

Script: [determine_inversions.py](#)

Output: [Indices_to_analyze/*](#): Gene inversions detected using phylogenetic and GC-skew-based approaches.

- Edit the core genome to only retain the clusters which show agreement in both approaches:

Script: [create_protcore_from_analysis.py](#)

Output: [reordered_coregenome.csv](#)

- Change protein ID-based headers for core genome to nucleotide ID (locus tag) based headers:

Script: [gen_nucl_tag_coregen.py](#)

Output: [nucleotide_coregenome.csv](#): final core genome with gene locus tags.

- Create core gene clusters based on nucleotide sequence, then repeat for protein sequence:

Script: [generate_clusters.py](#)

Output: [mafft_clust_nucl/*](#)
[mafft_clust_prot/*](#)

- Rename protein cluster headers to match the headers of nucleotide clusters:

Script: [rename_proteins.py](#)

Output: [mafft_clust_nucl/*](#)

- MAFFT based protein alignment:

Script: [align_proteins.py](#)

Output: [Protein_alignments/*](#)

- Protein to nucleotide alignment based on Pal2Nal:

Script: [pal2nal_clusters.py](#)

Output: [pal2nal_output/*](#)

- Concatenate the nucleotide alignments for phylogeny reconstruction:

Script: [concat_align.py](#)

Output: [IQtree_input/final_alignment.fasta](#)

- Run IQtree to get phylogeny:

Output: [IQtree_input/final_alignment.fasta.treefile](#): treefile generated by IQtree

- Generate paup input file to predict character state changes:

Script: [generate_paup_input.py](#)

Output: [IQtree_input/paupinput.nex](#): Input file for PAUP

- Run PAUP.

Output: [IQtree_input/paupout.log](#): log file with predicted ancestral states.

- Make character state files summarizing ingroup inversions. If there are no inversions, the code will generate an empty file. In the absence of root-node inversions, analysis concerning inversions can be stopped at this stage.

Script: [process_paup_output.py](#)
Output: [character_state_complete_list.csv](#)
[charstates_unidirectional_list.csv](#)

- Performing rotation of genome to align cluster number 0 at start position:

Script: [makerankordermatrix.py](#)
Output: [rankordermatrix_all/*](#)
[rankordermatrix_unidirectional/*](#)

- Mapping back inversions to a node and determination of contiguous events:

Script: [get_inversions_pernode.py](#)
Output: [events_list.txt](#)

- Get ancestral states:

Script: [ancestral_states.py](#)
Output: [cluster_ancestral_states.txt](#)

- Calculate size of inversion events:

Script: [eventsize.py](#)
Output: [event_size.txt](#)

2. Superoutgroup analysis

- Carry out superoutgroup analysis following the same steps till [makerankordermatrix.py](#)
- Create a mapping between super outgroup and ingroup analysis cluster numbers:

Script: [map_clusts_superout_to_out.py](#)
Output: [Outgroup-SupOutgroup_clustpairs.txt](#)

- Find ingroup node inversions from super outgroup:

Script: [get_root_inversions.py](#)
Output: [Root_Inversions_unfiltered.tsv](#)

- Filter root inversions to get only common root/ingroup node inversion:

Script: [extract_root_node_inversions.py](#)
Output: [Root_Inversions.tsv](#)

- Correct the ancestral states with root inversions:

Script: [root_correct_anc_states.py](#)

Output: [anc_states_root_corrected.txt](#)

[root_corrected_anc_state_summary.txt](#): number of core-genes with each orientation.

- Find inverted clusters and determine inversion types:

Script: [sort_inversions_single_multi.py](#)

Output: [/InversionType/*](#)

[/InversionType/singleInversions.tsv](#): cluster and node of single inversions.

- Split multi-inversions in parallel and revertant inversions:

Script: [sort_multi_inversions.py](#)

Output: [/InversionType/multiple_inv_types.txt](#): cluster and node of multiple inversions.

- Determine CD (leading)/HO (lagging) inversions post root correction and create a summary file:

Script: [determine_cd_ho_uni_inv.py](#)

Output: [/InversionType/unidirectional_summary_with_root.txt](#)

- Determine inversion events at the in-group node:

Script: [outgroup_inv_events.py](#)

Output: [outgroup_inversion_events.txt](#)

3) Recombination rate analysis:

- Remove outgroup from clusters:

Script: [filter_fasta_by_list_of_headers.py](#)

Output: [innuc_clust/*](#)

[inprot_clust/*](#)

- Protein alignment:

Script: [align_proteins.py](#)

Output: [inprot_aln/*](#)

- Protein to nucleotide alignment:

Script: [pal2nal_clusters.py](#)

Output: [innuc_aln/*](#)

- Concatenate the alignments:

Script: [concat_align.py](#)

Output: [phyML_input/ingroup_alignment.fasta](#)

- Run IQtree again with this alignment.

- Give generic strain numbers for phyML:

Script: [rename_fasta.py](#)
Output: [phyML_input/ingroup_alignment_renamed.aln](#)

- Change alignment format to Phylip for phyML:

Script: [fasta2phylip_aln.py](#)
Output: [phyML_input/ phylip.aln](#)

- Get Ts/Tv ratio by phyML:

Command: [phyml -i ../phyML_input/phylip.aln -t e](#)

- Change tags for every aligned cluster from protein ID to Locus tag-based ID:

Script: [return_genome_tags.py](#)
Output: [clonalframeml_input/*](#)

- Move files to a folder named clonalframeml_input. Following steps can be run from the same folder:

- Convert format from paml to fasta:

Script: [paml2fasta.sh](#)

- Perform ClonalFrameML (edit the bash file with Ts/Tv ratio (kappa) estimated from PhyML before running for each species):

Script: [./clonalFrameML_loop.sh](#)

- Summarize data for each species. Move the code to output folder and execute the script:

Script: [recomb_sum.sh](#)
Output: [/clonalframeml_output/summary.txt](#)

3. Kingdom-wide analysis:

- GC-skew based ori-ter prediction, gene directionality prediction, and inversion detection were carried out using genomic fasta and feature table files, using the following script. This script calls [inversion_strand_combined_analysis.py](#) and [findori_windowcontrol_inv_kingdomwide.out](#) internally.

Script: [invert_strand_analysis_loop.py](#)
Output: [/originresults/resultsummary.txt](#)

- Summarize the gene-directionality and inversions data:

Script: [direction_count.py](#)
Output: [/originresults/count_summary.csv](#)

- Run repeat-match for all the genomes to be analyzed.

- Process the repeat-match output. The script requires origin and terminus predictions as prerequisite.

Script: [parse_mummer_kingdom.py](#)

Output: [filename.output.parsed](#): parsed repeat-match file containing distance, nature and type of repeat.

- Preparatory calculations for strand switch potential. Outputs the summation of repeat length multiplied by spacer length as SS_numerator and total length of repeats as SS_denominator. Ni_SS is the number of repeats used in the calculation. (The second script performs an identical function for repeats with at least 1 kb spacer length.)

Script: [SS_calc_prep.py](#)

Output: [/SS_results/SS_prep_summary.txt](#)

Script: [SS_calc_prep_over_1kb_spacer.py](#)

Output: [/SS_results/SS_prep_summary_over_1kb.txt](#)

- Calculate SSxNi by following formula = (SS_numerator / (SS_denominator x Genome length)) x Ni_SS

4. Repeat-match (Mummer) based analysis of repeats:

- Make sequence scrambled genomes:

Script: [seq_randomizer.py](#)

- Run repeat-match for reference genome and randomized genomes:

Output: filename.output:

- Process the repeat-match output. The script requires origin and terminus predictions as prerequisite.

Script: [parse_mummer.py](#)

Output: [filename.output.parsed](#): parsed repeat-match file containing distance, nature and type of repeat.

5. palindrome (EMBOSS) based analysis of repeats:

- Run palindrome with following parameters: (-minpallen 20 -maxpallen 100 -gaplimit (length of genome) -nooverlap)
- Parse the palindrome output to get repeat co-ordinates, determine inter/intra-replichore nature of repeat pairs:

Script: [parse_palindrome.py](#)

Output: [filename.output.parsed](#): parsed repeat-match file containing distance, nature and type of repeat.